

HOSPITAL FINDER APP

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Abstract - The Hospital Finder App is an excellent multi-function application developed to make healthcare services manageable for the users. This application includes features such as user Registration and Login for security purposes. Users are first redirected to Home screen, after they log into the system or get authenticated. Home screen has provisions such as Find Hospital, Lab Test, Buy Medicine, Health Articles, and Order Details. Each module allows the user to interact easily with the common Database (DB) and allows easy access to the stored data.

A particular Find Hospital module allows users to search for available hospital and other healthcare units within their vicinity. Also, the features Lab Test and Buy Medicine enable users to book and pay for lab services and buy drugs online and such information is recorded under Order Details. Also, users are able to read articles regarding health issues so that they can increase their awareness using the Health Articles section. The app has been developed in a manner that it's impossible for the user to lose focus and all of the transactions are strongly tracked; when the transaction is completed, there is a clear Logout option to end the session safely.

The system architecture of such a system is built to be comprehensive, easy-to-use, and effective so the users do not have to use multiple systems for the same thing, and for healthcare in this case, one is enough. This project focuses on the gap in the market for combined health services which is technologically savvy and does not compromise on the patient experience.

Keywords: Healthcare Accessibility, Medical Facility Search, Emergency Services, Patient Navigation, Real-time Availability, Appointment Booking, User Safety, Medical Specialization finder.

I. INTRODUCTION

By integrating multiple healthcare functions, The Hospital Finder App is a health management app which helps patients to reach out to vital health services easily. In the contemporary world, getting health services, booking a lab appointment, buying medications, as well dependable health information, is not easy. This app integrates all these services on one platform therefore making it easy for users, efficient and accessible.

The Issuance of an ID Certificate is the first step, it helps the user to keep their data secure during the retrieval and storage, so the user first registers and logs in onto the system. After signing in, the Home dashboard provides people with diverse functionalities such as Find Hospital, which helps users find a place in a hospital that is close to them. Additionally, the dashboard also has Lab Test Booking system, which allows users to set up an appointment to visit the lab, or Buy Medicine. All the activities that the user does are recorded and managed by a central server which is known as the Database and Order Details module.

The healthcare finder application employs effective modern form design and performance technology. Every element has a unique purpose that has been designed specifically for the users making it possible for them to quickly meet their critical healthcare needs. Additionally, this system reduces the duration spent by patients in the queue thereby increasing the number of people that are eligible to get medical attention from the professionals that are present.

II. RELATED WORK

Offers a telemedicine technology alongside an Emergency Response System that integrates both pre-hospital and in-facility care. Suggests a single mobile health solution that incorporates all components of healthcare, including pre-hospital care and care at a facility, through the use of telecommunications and

devices such as the emergency response system. The lack of trained personnel in the different sub sectors, variability in the infrastructure, and fragmentation of service delivery systems are the major reasons why this has not been realized. While other people may be inadequate personnel and infrastructure. [1]

The rationale of the Hospital Finder App is design comparison to the Increasing demand for health care service delivery during an emergency period. In emergencies, people can find it a lifesaving technique to identify the closest hospital or medical center within reach. Many people are unable to use such facilities simply because they are in a different location, it is an odd hour of the night, or it is a stressful situation and those people do not know where to go. These challenges can be made worse by the absence of information that is integrated, timely and up to date in respect of hospitals, which will have such things as geography of location, provision of services, and ratings. The aim of the app is to address these problems by making it easier for those that have difficulties to obtain healthcare services when, where, and how they need them [2].

Healthcare choices can be complex and it is usually people seeking help to address their healthcare needs or even acute care who are in need of a healthcare provider. The factors that guide such decision making include distance, the standing of the hospital, range of facilities and services, and cost of services but this information without a tool can be hard to get. The Hospital Finder App, however, addresses this issue by providing users an ability to sort the options according to their requirements and preferences, thereby speedily bringing a user to the best hospital. This is helpful in making many important judgments which otherwise can be a bit difficult, but increases a person's experience of overall healthcare. [3]

Furthermore, in the context of problems of world globalization including the demographic problem and the growth of medical problems, there is a need for better access to medical facilities and providers. In response to this challenge, the Hospital Finder App proposes an intelligent, real-time solution, using geolocation and other data to offer tailored recommendations to users. The aim is not only to present users with a tool to locate the hospital, but also to improve how and where healthcare is provided through technology so as to achieve better outcomes and user experience in terms of population health and patient health. [4]

Health direct Australia provides a comprehensive health application which users can use to get health information, a symptom checker, and a service finder. The application includes educational content and tools to find a healthcare service in a way that the user will make an informed decision.[5]

The barriers, including service fragmentation, poor infrastructure and insufficient trained staff can be turned down with this application. It also aims at integrating mobile health applications with emergency response systems and in the same time fostering teamwork across medical practitioners to improve health outcomes for the population. However mobile interconnectivity and data synchronization still continue to be persistent issues.[6]

The COVID 19 pandemic pointed out the need for streamlined healthcare information systems. A study by Johnson et al. (2021) established that during the pandemic, hospitality and resource status applications were critical in controlling patient influx. This review again emphasizes the creation of programs such as Hospital Finder which seeks to optimize the search for scarce health care services in real time.[7]

We can describe it as 'knowledge management system' design which has the potential of improving medical diagnosis and treatment by the use of expertise sharing. It also entails a considerable degree of working together from multiple medical teams, which proved to be a challenge in the real sense of it. Indeed collaboration across medical teams is challenging in practice. Very heavy reliance on mobile interconnectivity. This is a major challenge in - synchronizing real time data between private hospitals and government hospitals. The same can be said about that when you try to apply different medical turbines.

Connect mobile health apps with a universal medical dispatching system that will allow users to reach out nearest hospitals quickly. [8]

Some healthcare apps enable users to schedule a visit with a doctor. In the case of regular patients this can be a useful feature, but these applications often do not have any advanced tools for tracking a doctor's schedule or the number of patients a hospital can take. Also, they usually do not address emergency demands, which can include searching for free specialists or even unoccupied beds.[9]

Alert the user about an alarm in an emergency that a user has done, and it directly informs about nearby hospitals and ambulances that are connected to a central system. There are practical difficulties of this technology, as well as extreme disadvantages. The Hospital Finder App aims to tackle problems that people face in accessing timely healthcare services during an emergency and general health services by creating a single platform with accurate and real time information, using app and providing filters based on people's needs to improve health care accessibility, services and satisfaction.[10]

III. METHODOLOGY

The Hospital Finder App's architecture is aimed at improving the effectiveness of the user searching for the medical service. The application comprises a mixture of front end and backend components supplemented by security and data management layers. The following gives a description of the system architecture.

User Interface (UI):

The app's front end has an easy to understand and use interface that is user friendly. The front end uses HTML, JavaScript and React.js and allows users to book hospitals, buy medicine and book lab test services from the features. The layout is flexible and therefore is easily adjusted to work on a cell phone, a tablet or a desktop computer.

Communication Support Layer:

This layer is involved with the interface between the submission of market and communicational items in a client's hardware and the execution of the tasks in the server. It enables efficient transfer of data whereby users are able to perform hospital search, place orders and read health articles among other functionalities on the system.

Backend Layer:

The business logic, user requests, and database interaction are managed by a Node.js and Express.js core backend layer with a focus on simplicity. Users are able to conduct a number of critical functions within the app, such as looking up hospitals, ordering medications, and making appointments for laboratory tests. The wise avoiding design also guarantees that all machines perform their functions effectively.

Core Backend & Functional Modules:

The backend layer is connected with a number of essential functional modules that are required to perform the main functions of the application:

- **Comprehensive Hospital Search Module:** Use the information such as location, specialty, and services available to locate and show relevant hospitals to users.
- **Medicine Purchase Module:** Support online medicine purchases, such as selecting medicines, order medicines, and paying the order.
- **Lab Test Booking Module:** Users can book their lab tests by searching for a category of tests and by scheduling the appointment.
- **Health Articles Module:** Stores both articles related to health as well as wellness and treatment options.

Security & Privacy Layer:

The system has provided SSL/TLS encryption for the safe transfer of client-server. Also, AES encryption is in place for the safe custody of sensitive user information such as medical information, order particulars and personal information. This layer assures user data will be kept confidential and unblemished throughout all the interactions.

Real-Time Monitoring & Alert System:

There is an independent system that observes user's activities across the system and their interactions in order to make alerts for the users for crucial touch points. For example, when receiving an order for a medicine from a user or scheduling a testing procedure in a diagnostic laboratory, there are live updates sent through Firebase Cloud Messaging (FCM) or Twilio to the user regarding the status changes, confirmations or reminders.

Real-Time Reporting System:

The app provides the reports on usage frequency, trends of patients' queries to search for hospitals and the rate of lab tests ordering at the time. These reports are analyzed and featured on the screen of the health sector specialists' dashboard for easy interfacing of the patients and optimization of the services. In addition, these reports can be forwarded to the healthcare authorities via RESTful APIs or GraphQL for policy formulation.

Community Forum:

Users can engage in a variety of activities, including sharing their experiences with other people or using a community forum that is built on Node.js and backed up with SQL or MongoDB. Further, people can talk about medical issues and review hospitals while still receiving help in a moderated and controlled space.

Progressive Web Apps (PWA):

In order to keep the app responsive across devices, the developers made sure to incorporate Progressive Web apps into the technology stack that was designed around React Native or Ionic frameworks. Not only are they able to make the app experience mobile-first but users are also able to use the app without Internet on browsing as well as using the app's features. Hence, users are able to get the information about healthcare and any services in a constant manner without being hindered by an Internet connection.

IV. LEARNT DECISIONS

The Hospital Finder App, meticulously designed keeping the user front in mind, enabled users to engage in easy app navigation as well as app functionality. Other such decisions, including enabling geolocation to search hospitals in real-time, enhancing scalability with MySQL and MongoDB, and incorporating SSL/TLS to increase security measures, have made a great deal of impact in functionality and user experience as well.

V. EXCEPTED OUTCOME

User Authentication and Registration:

Creating basic, mean log in and registration form where the users can manage their log in information, which in return is stored on the database (DB). Also Successful user can be validated and user data can also be stored during the registration process.

Hospital Finder Feature:

The user can use a 'Find Hospital' feature on the application to look up their hospitals in a certain area or of the area or scope of practice that the user wants.

Healthcare Services Integration:

Through a universal dashboard, the user can conveniently access features such as Lab Test booking, Medicine purchasing, and Health Articles User's data and requests for the service are easily and efficiently passed back and forth between the app and the database.

Order Management System:

The tracking of which the user performed activities on (for example purchasing of medicine or booking a lab test), is integrated into a new Order Details section.

Data Management and Storage:

A secure Database (DB) for user's data, health service requests, and transaction information is ensured through the use of a strong database (DB).

User-Friendly Navigation:

Users of the app can effortlessly move between different features like Home, service features (e.g., Find Hospital, Buy Medicine), and Logout by means of the basic structure of the app.

VI. CHALLENGES

Some of the weaknesses perceived in the framework such as, user login, database management, flow design, data sharing, user interface, growth, and confidentiality, are some of the areas which need to be considered in the workings of the system. In doing so, it would be a matter of enhancing security, increasing the efficiency of the database and improving the design of the system so that users can use it easily.

User Authentication and Management:

- Define the methods of secure login and registration.
- Correct verification of the users' input and its storage in the DB.

Database Connectivity and Integration:

- Prepare and link the Registration and Order Details with the DB without failure.
- Quick access to data for doctor's ordering Laboratory tests, buying medicines as well as searching for hospitals.

Complex Navigation Flow:

- Efficient Routing of the user around other modules like on Home page articles and On Health Articles page users clicks the Logout Link.
- Prevent swerving or endless navigation in the system.

Data Management in Order Details:

- Multi Process workflow integration such as Lab Tests, Orders of Medicines and Searching of the Hospitals.
- Managing overlapping data from multiple processes like data representation in Order Details module.

VII. CONCLUSION

The integrated approach of the Hospital Finder App is such that healthcare service seekers need not search for resources separately. It covers all the essential links of healthcare services in an easy-to-use app. It is easy to use due to the simple design of the application which requires no technical skills from the user. It uses geolocation method to allow a fast-searching real time of the hospitals closest to the user, and this feature makes the application suitable for urgent cases. This fluidity is due to the easy and quick interface that allows users to use the services without complexity.

With the use of MySQL and MongoDB, the app is able to provide a strong and efficient core infrastructure that allows for the maintenance of user data, hospital information and the information of the transactions. This has the advantage that as the number of users and the number of hospitals and the services being increased, this database would allow for the growth in capacity. Sensitive user data will always be protected first by implementing SSL or TLS encryption whenever information is being transmitted and AES encryption whenever there is stored sensitive private medical information. All private information is kept secret and neutralizes any abuse given the mentioned features. Moreover, the application's real-time messaging system actively updates users on their status including the status of their search in the hospitals, lab test bookings and medicine orders.

Web-based mobile applications (PWAs) in particular appeal as they allow all users irrespective of the type of device they use to interact with the platform on their mobile or desktop devices without having to install

additional applications. This has been possible by adopting a mobile-first strategy which improves the overall user experience by making healthcare resources available. The app is built on a modular architecture allowing it to be updated and expanded as the needs of users and the healthcare industry evolve. This ensures more usability, security, and scalability of the Hospital Finder App that provides an effective way to take care of health related needs.

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